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Abbreviations list

API	Application Programming Interface
BELSPO	Belgian Science Policy Office / Federal Science Policy Office
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DC	Dublin Core
DCS	DMP Common Standard
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP-IF	Data Management Plan-Interoperability Framework
DMPQV	Data Management Plan Quality Vocabulary
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERC	European Research Council
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FR	Functional Requirements
FWF	Österreichischer Wissenschaftsfonds / Austrian Science Fund
FWO	Fonds voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek – Vlaanderen / Research Foundation – Flanders
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
IF	Interoperability Framework
IF/RA	Interoperability Framework/Reference Architecture
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data

maDMP Machine Actionable Data Management Plan

NCN Narodowe Centrum Nauki / National Science Centre

NSF National Science Foundation

NWO Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek / Dutch Research Council

OAI-PMH Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

UGent Universiteit Gent / Ghent University

UML Unified Modelling Language

PID Permanent Identifier

PROV PROV Vocabulary

PTA Plan-Track-Assess

RA Reference Architecture

RDA Research Data Alliance

RUP Rational Unified Process

SE Science Europe

SKG Scientific Knowledge Graph

SKG-IF Scientific Knowledge Graph-Interoperability Framework

SND Swedish National Data Service

UC Use Case

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Executive Summary

The increasing adoption of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) represents a significant advancement in research data management (RDM). By enabling automation, interoperability, and machine-readability, maDMPs streamline the planning, sharing, and assessment of research data and related outputs. Despite their potential, the lack of standardised evaluation frameworks and services poses challenges in ensuring that maDMPs are complete, relevant, and aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and Open Science principles.

This deliverable addresses these challenges by defining a robust evaluation framework for maDMPs and developing a DMP Evaluation Service Specification. The framework leverages existing standards, such as the Science Europe rubric and national guidelines, to provide clear criteria for assessing the effectiveness of maDMPs in achieving research objectives. In addition, the deliverable outlines the technical specifications and metrics required to automate this evaluation, ensuring interoperability with existing DMP platforms, project reporting systems, and other platforms.

The scope of this work extends beyond simply evaluating maDMPs. It aims to validate these plans by linking persistent identifiers (PIDs) embedded in the maDMPs to corresponding knowledge graphs (SKGs), enabling FAIR and domain-specific assessments. The envisioned system will support diverse research contexts by offering tailored profiles that account for disciplinary differences and research stages, including planning and near-completion phases.

To achieve these objectives, a multi-faceted methodology was adopted. The development of the maDMP evaluation framework began with a landscape analysis to assess the current state of evaluation practices and identify gaps. This was followed by in-depth desk research that examined existing rubrics and standards, including those developed by Science Europe and relevant initiatives of national funders, institutions or thematic research infrastructures. Co-creation activities were conducted in collaboration with key stakeholders engaged via the project's pilots, ensuring that the framework reflects the needs of diverse research communities.

The deliverable is organised into six main sections, each covering a distinct aspect of the work. Section 1 describes the methodology employed in developing the evaluation framework. Section 2 defines the maDMP Evaluation Framework, covering both conceptual and technical components. Section 3 identifies gaps and opportunities, offering recommendations for improvement. Section 4 outlines the upcoming activities and next steps in the project. Section 5 provides the conclusion, summarising key findings and future directions.

1 Introduction

DMP evaluation today involves assessing plans based on completeness, quality, and adherence to specific funder or institutional requirements. These evaluations are primarily manual and focus on checking whether key elements of data management are addressed, such as data sharing, storage, and long-term preservation. Tools like ARGOS, DAMAP and DSW developed by partners of the OSTrails consortium, assist researchers in creating DMPs, but the process remains labour-intensive and often inconsistent across different research contexts. Additionally, many of the existing evaluation rubrics focus on qualitative assessments, requiring human reviewers to determine whether DMPs are feasible and in line with best practices.

Several rubrics are available for DMP evaluation, with the [Science Europe DMP Template](#) being one of the most widely used across Europe. This rubric provides a comprehensive set of criteria for assessing various aspects of DMPs, such as data storage, sharing, and preservation plans. However, it lacks flexibility in addressing the specific needs of different research disciplines or research stages, which limits its adaptability. Similarly, national rubrics have emerged, tailored to local research needs and legal frameworks. While they address region-specific challenges like data privacy, these rubrics often lack standardisation, making it difficult to compare or integrate them across different countries and disciplines.

Another significant framework is the [RDA DMP Common Standard](#), which aims to standardise DMP structures using machine-readable formats like JSON. The adoption of the Common Standard resulted in creating interoperable DMPs that can be easily integrated across systems. However, even then there are challenges when attempting to harmonise with the more qualitative aspects of evaluation, such as assessing the quality of a researcher's planning, feasibility, or alignment with research objectives [6, 7].

Traditional rubrics, such as Science Europe, rely on qualitative assessments, such as determining whether a DMP is feasible or aligns with best practices. These subjective evaluations are inherently difficult to automate and assess computationally. In contrast, quantitative criteria (e.g., "Does the DMP include a data sharing plan?") are easier to evaluate but don't fully capture the nuances of a high-quality DMP.

Furthermore, most of the rubrics were developed for human reviewers, with text-heavy descriptions and checklists that are not designed for machine interpretation. Even when these rubrics are converted into structured formats, such as XML or JSON, they often become unwieldy or fail to cover all the aspects required for a full evaluation in an automated manner. This incompatibility with machine actionability presents a significant challenge for adopting these rubrics into maDMP systems. Many rubrics require a more nuanced evaluation that goes beyond the simple completion of a checklist, making them difficult to automate without losing essential evaluative criteria.

From a policy perspective, the integration of rubrics into maDMPs faces hurdles related to legal frameworks, data privacy, and national compliance requirements. Different regions have varying regulations regarding data governance, which directly impacts the design and implementation of machine-actionable frameworks. For instance, GDPR in Europe requires data protection protocols to be carefully planned and documented, a challenge that existing rubrics do not always address comprehensively. This necessitates additional technical layers in maDMPs to ensure compliance, further complicating the implementation of a universal framework across multiple jurisdictions.

Technically, moving to maDMPs requires addressing the need for interoperability between various systems and the automation of the evaluation process. [8] This can be complicated by the diversity of the rubrics in use and the often rigid, non-standardised formats they employ. The shift towards machine-actionable formats involves addressing issues of data structure consistency, the creation of standardised APIs, and integration with existing research management platforms. Furthermore, developing a system that balances between comprehensive data management planning and machine-readability is a technical challenge that has yet to be fully resolved.

1. Methodology

Our work consists of both **technical** (service) and **conceptual** (rubrics) developments, hence the methodology combined multiple research approaches to ensure a comprehensive and well-informed framework for Data Management Plan (DMP) evaluation. The process was structured around three key components: **Desk Research, Co-creation, and Service Design**, each contributing to a holistic understanding of existing practices, stakeholder needs, and service implementation requirements.

1.1 Landscape analysis

Our landscape activities focused on desk research and input gathered from project pilot partners, resulting to thorough analysis and practical feedback that informed the final version of the deliverable.

1.1.1 Desk Research

Initially, we focused on the collection, comparison, and analysis of templates, rubrics, and relevant guidance from successful examples starting from the Science Europe. The goal was to identify common elements, differences, and gaps between the standards used for Data Management Plans (DMPs).

The data was recorded in Excel, where different sheets were used for the questions, rubrics, and guidance respectively. This organisation allowed for easy comparison between the collected material ([See Annex](#)). Each column in the table represented a different organisation or initiative, and the mapping process enabled a clear alignment of

each question with the corresponding elements of the Science Europe Template. After completing the mapping, the main observations were recorded in a Word document.

1.1.2 Co-creation

In this phase of our landscaping activity, emphasis was placed on collaboration and communication with all the pilot participants, ensuring their active involvement in shaping the results. To complete the mapping process, the Excel file was shared with the project's pilot participants. They provided material used by their funding organisations (funders) or institutions that were missing from the initial desk research, such as templates, which included questions for DMPs, as well as the corresponding rubrics and guidance (where applicable).

1.2 Service design

To design the DMP evaluation framework we based our work on identifying the key challenges in the current DMP evaluation process and established the requirements for the new framework, defining the quality dimensions in which the service will perform the evaluation. We then designed the business processes based on exemplar use cases and a defined data structure that describes the results of the DMP evaluation.

2 Definition of the maDMP Evaluation Framework

The maDMP Evaluation Framework consists of two key components: the **evaluation service** itself and the **criteria and standards** that inform its operation. These two elements must work together to enable a comprehensive and automated evaluation of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs). The evaluation service provides the infrastructure for automated assessments, while the rubrics, templates, and guidance supply the necessary content and criteria that the service uses.

We focus on assessing the **completeness, quality, and validation** of Data Management Plans (DMPs) within the context of **machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs)** ensuring that DMPs not only meet baseline requirements but also adhere to best practices, such as the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It incorporates both quantitative and qualitative criteria to assess different aspects of a DMP's dimensions. While quantitative criteria can verify the presence of specific elements, such as data-sharing plans, qualitative aspects are crucial for assessing the depth and applicability of these elements within different research contexts.

The following sections outline the distinct but complementary areas of work involved in developing and implementing the maDMP evaluation system.

2.1 Technical Specifications (Service Development)

This category focuses on the **technical development and operationalisation** of the maDMP evaluation service. It involves the creation and implementation of the **service infrastructure** that supports the automation of DMP evaluations. Key tasks include:

- **Designing the evaluation service:** Developing the system that automates the evaluation of maDMPs, ensuring that it can process and assess DMPs efficiently.
- **Integrating the service:** Connecting the evaluation service with existing tools, platforms, and infrastructures (e.g., research data repositories, Open Science frameworks) to ensure compatibility and smooth operation.
- **Defining functional requirements:** Establishing the technical criteria and data quality dimensions that the service must address to ensure accurate evaluations.
- **Operationalising the service:** Ensuring the service is scalable, efficient, and user-friendly, and that it can process DMPs from various research contexts.

Figure 1 shows the current state of the art (AS-IS) and presents two possible solutions for automating the review process. The (AS-IS) scenario is where the maDMP is converted into a text-based document that answers the questions of the funder's template, and the reviewer performs the work manually as described above. The TO-BE-1 scenario shows the scenario where researchers use their current workflow to produce a maDMP and send it to the funder who has the DMP Evaluation service, this software provides structured and human readable information and metrics to assist reviewers in their evaluation and reduce the amount of manual research needed to provide contextual information. Scenario TO-Be -2 illustrates the situation where researchers can benefit from the automated evaluation of the DMP prior to submission, this can help researchers to identify weaknesses in their DMPs.

Figure 1- Current DMP evaluation scenario (AS-IS) and possible scenarios for automation on maDMP evaluation (TO-BE).

Based on the previous scenarios, we present three exemplar use cases for the DMP evaluation service (**Figure 2**).

UC1 Generate Measurements: User generates quality measurements for a given DMP which includes loading a maDMP from diverse sources and parsing it into a normalised format. In addition, information from linked resources and other data sources needed to generate measurements can be retrieved to provide context for the evaluation, which is an extension of the base use case for measurement generation. The process of generating DMP evaluation metrics depends on the specific evaluation requirements, and the service must accommodate different scenarios based on the evaluation goals.

UC2 Retrieve Measurements: User retrieves the result of past evaluations without the need to recalculate the measurements. Measurements should be stored and made available to other actors and services.

UC3 Generate Evaluation Report: To assist reviewers in the evaluation of DMPs, the system provides the ability to combine measurements to provide a higher-level evaluation result. The aggregation of measurements includes the selection of measurements based on a set of metrics, dimensions, or categories. In addition to this aggregation, the report contains other relevant information on the evaluation, such as

the evaluated domain, the context harvested, and the measurements generated with their corresponding metric definitions.

Figure 2 - Use cases for the automated evaluation of DMPs.

Furthermore, we present the workflows that correspond to the use cases defined and focus on the execution of the processes involved in specifying and configuring these automated actions. **Figure 3** shows a high-level overview of the business process involved.

Figure 3 - Overview of processes of the DMP Evaluation Service.

The processes involved are:

1. **Evaluator Configuration:** Review experts configure the solution, providing domain knowledge that allows later measurement generation. This includes the definition of metrics and the evaluation context, as well as the configuration of evaluation methods.
2. **Evaluation:** The solution automatically generates indicators on a given DMP based on the configuration resulting from the process *Evaluator Configuration*.

3. **Evaluation Report:** To integrate the solution into the broader RDM infrastructure of an institution, the solution provides access to the generated indicators in a standardised format as well as methods to query individual measurements and aggregated information of these measurements.

These three processes are made up of further sub-processes, which will be discussed in the rest of this section.

Evaluator Configuration

The workflow of configuring the evaluation framework is pictured in **Figure 4** and consists of the following steps to be carried out by the domain expert:

Figure 4 - Evaluator configuration process.

1. **Define Evaluation Context:** DCS DMPs contain references to external resources that contain the information mentioned. In addition to explicit references to other data sources, the information contained in a DMP can be enriched with information from a variety of resources which must be identified and mapped.
2. **Define Evaluation Metrics:** Different stakeholders have different evaluations and quality guidelines regarding DMPs and, therefore, no framework can produce all the indicators required for the use cases of each reviewer. Therefore, in this process, review experts define specific indicators and the respective unit of the resulting measurements to cover their needs. Furthermore, DMPs can be available at different stages of the life cycle of research data, containing different granularities of information, which also leads to the need to provide different metrics depending on the lifecycle phase. Therefore, when defining indicators, the lifecycle phase in which they can be measured should be considered.
3. **Configure Evaluation Methods:** After the form of the required indicators is defined, the semantics for creating measurements of them have to be specified. To this regard, domain experts provide definitions for evaluators with the goal of defining how quality measurements for the previously elicited metrics will be produced.
4. **Validate Configuration:** Before persisting with the configuration, it must be validated itself to ensure that all the definitions in the configuration are consistent and sufficiently cover the evaluation requirements.

5. **Persist Configuration:** At the end of the configuration workflow, the resulting artifacts will be persisted to be used by the evaluation framework to provide the specified metrics in subsequent business processes.

Evaluation Process

Given a valid configuration, the evaluation process shown in **Figure 5** generates and provides quality measurements for a given DMP. The following sub-processes are involved:

Figure 5 - Evaluation Process.

1. **Load Configuration:** The configuration exported as a result of the Evaluator Configuration workflow described before will be instantiated and deployed as part of the evaluation solution.
2. **Load DMP:** The DMP for which indicators should be provided will be loaded into the environment.
3. **Fetch DMP Context:** The contextual information provided by the loaded configuration will be fetched according to the given configuration.
4. **Specify Lifecycle:** As outlined in the Evaluator Configuration workflow, indicators depend on the current life cycle phase. Therefore, before generating any indicator measurements, reviewers must provide the DMP lifecycle phase to apply the given metrics.
5. **Evaluation:** This process produces the measurements for the given indicators according to the given configuration.
6. **Persist Measurements:** At the end of the evaluation process, the measurements will be stored together with the metadata of the corresponding metric.

Evaluation Report

To provide a measurable result, these measurements can be aggregated to provide an Evaluation Report to reviewers. **Figure 6** shows the business process associated with the provision of these reports, including the following steps:

Figure 6- Evaluation Report process.

1. **Load Measurements:** The quality measurement of an evaluated DMP will be fetched from storage.
2. **Generate Report:** A report will be generated by selecting measurement for certain metrics, dimensions, or categories and aggregating and averaging them values.
3. **Share Report:** Finally, the selected indicators together with the previously calculated aggregations and averages will be exported for further use.

2.1.1 Functional Requirements and Data Quality Dimensions

This section lists the functional requirements based on the use cases for the DMP Evaluation Service.

Table 1 - Functional Requirements.

FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS	USE CASE	IMPACT
FR1 Load maDMP	The service must be able to integrate arbitrary services that provide DMPs and load those maDMPs so that they can be accessed by different services.	Interoperability of maDMPs across maDMP providers; Increased accessibility
FR2 Fetch Context	The service must be able to extend the information of the given DMP with additional contextual data and store the result so that it can be accessed in the future.	Enhanced metadata; long-term retrieval; AI-readiness

FR3 Connect to SKGs and Repositories	The service must provide the possibility to access the context that has been collected for a DMP.	Interoperability; Semantics; AI-readiness
FR4 Produce Measurements	The service must provide the possibility to produce quality measurements for DMP, given the maDMP to be evaluated, the data model underlying the maDMP to be evaluated, information about what quality dimensions should be included in the evaluation and contextual information for the given maDMP.	Quality assurance
FR5 Connect to External Evaluators	The service must enable the integration of external evaluation services such, as FAIR evaluators, independent of their implementation details.	Flexibility; Scalability; Interoperability
FR6 Generate Measurements	The service must be able to retrieve the measurements generated from the evaluation of a maDMP.	Provenance; Accessibility
FR7 Export Measurements	The service must be able to store the quality measurements and provide access so that other services can access them after the evaluation.	Increased accessibility
FR8 Export Evaluation Metadata	Not only is the result of the application of a quality indicator of interest, but more information is needed to qualitatively represent the evaluation output. Therefore, the solution must be able to provide access to further evaluation and provenance information.	Provenance; Semantics
FR9 Generate Evaluation Report	The system must provide the possibility to generate evaluation reports from already existing measurements from a previous execution of the DMP evaluation. These reports should collect all information resulting from the evaluation, namely the evaluated DMP, the corresponding context, and the generated measurements.	Publishing; semantics; AI-readiness
FR10 Aggregate Measurements	The system must be able to provide aggregations on the measurements generated.	Granularity

To complement this, we describe the categories and the quality dimensions in which the service performs the evaluation. The data quality dimensions are the evaluation objectives of the DMP evaluation service.

- **Completeness:** In the context of DCS DMPs, completeness can be further distinguished by the standard used as a baseline for completeness. The RDA proposed DCS as a minimum standard that maDMPs must meet to enable interoperability between RDM systems. Therefore, completeness with respect to this standard is a separate verification dimension *n*, namely DCS completeness. As the DCS does not cover all aspects of individual stakeholder needs, the completeness of a DCS DMP with respect to arbitrary extensions is identified as a separate completeness dimension, Extension Completeness. Both completeness dimensions measure the extent to which necessary information is present in the maDMP and to provide measures for these dimensions.
- **Feasibility:** This category is attributed to the three quality dimensions *Accuracy*, *Availability* and *Consistency*.
 - **Accuracy:** Refers to the degree to which the data values correctly represent real-world facts. In the context of maDMP evaluation, this implies comparing the values of the given maDMP with some ground truth.
 - **Availability:** Refers to the degree to which a resource referenced in a DMP can be accessed. This contrasts with the *Accessibility* principle of the FAIR principles, which provides information on how easy it is to access and use the data and focuses more on the available information describing accessibility properties of the digital object.
 - **Consistency:** This evaluates the logical coherence of maDMPs both internally and with external standards.
- **Quality of Actions:** For this category *Accessibility*, *Portability*, *Licensing* and *Compatibility* have been identified as dimensions. Because the dimensions included in this category are highly dependent on the applicable community standards, we opted to use the dimensions *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable* of the FAIR principles [3].
 These principles are already widely used in the assessment of the quality of a wide range of digital objects, especially in the research domain. When applying FAIR metrics on DCS DMPs we propose to distinguish between quality measurements on the DMP itself and measurements for the included datasets. Another distinction can be made whether the given resource is published or not. In case the DMP is published, actual FAIR metrics can be produced, and if not only predictions on the expected FAIRness and guidance can be inferred.
- **Compliance:** In the scope of DCS DMPs the *Compliance* of a DMP is dependent on the given requirements. Therefore, we identified three categories of regulatory sources that can provide compliance constraints for evaluation, which, in turn, constitute the dimensions of this evaluation category:
 - **Guidelines:** Guidelines regarding the contents of DMPs are published by various entities such as funding bodies, universities and other stakeholders involved in the management of research data. An example of a funder guideline is the Science Europe Evaluation Rubric [1], which provides the core requirements for DMPs, criteria for the selection of trustworthy

repositories, and guidance for researchers to comply with organisational requirements.

- **DMP Common Standard (DCS):** maDMPs should follow a common data model to allow interoperability. As DMP Common Standard (DCS) is the maDMP standard endorsed by the RDA its constraints are compliance requirements for the evaluation of maDMPs.
- **DCS Extensions:** The authors of the DCS application profile for maDMPs recognised the need for extensions to the standard to cover application specific needs.

2.1.2 Building Block Design

This section provides a static decomposition of the system to describe the behaviour of these building blocks as scenarios covering important use cases from the requirements given.

To show the static decomposition of the system into building blocks and to make the structure of the proposed DMP evaluation framework understandable through abstraction, **Figure 7** shows a high-level overview of the services included in the proposed system, as well as the connections between them. In the remainder of this section, we give an overview of the components of the proposed framework, including a description of their purpose, exposed interfaces, and interactions with external actors and services. Some components are composed of subcomponents for which we also provide more detailed explanations.

Figure 7 - High - level building block view.

DMP Loader

This component is responsible for connecting the DMP evaluation framework external *DMP Sources* and providing the information contained in these sources in the form of the

DMP itself. As a result, the component provides the normalised maDMP. As a result, the component provides the normalised maDMP as well as the underlying DCS ontology and extension ontologies and abstracts the interaction with the *DMP Source*

To provide access to this collected information to other components in the framework, the *DMP Loader* exposes the interfaces *Load DMP* to provide the maDMP for a given identifier, *Load DCS Ontology* to provide the underlying DCS ontology of the maDMP and *Load Extension Ontologies* to provide a list of extensions included in the DMP with the given identifier.

Context Loader

Provides contextual information for a given DMP by collecting and returning information from external sources such as *SKGs* and *Data Repositories* in a uniform format. We propose to make use of the proposed *Evaluation Context* data structure that is going to be present at the end of the section as part of data architecture. The component exposes the interface *Load DMP Context*, which accepts a maDMP and returns a list of context objects that the *Context Loader* provides.

Data Store

The *Data Store* provides the ability to persist data and unify access to them in a way that is agnostic to the underlying format or technology used. In particular, it provides the ability to store and access maDMPs, the evaluation context, and the evaluation measurements resulting from the evaluation of a DMP.

Evaluator

The *Evaluator* component performs the actual calculations to generate quality metrics for a given DMP. In addition to a DMP that includes the associated ontologies of the underlying standard and included extensions, it can also receive evaluation context to have access to additional information related to the DMP. The way in which the evaluator generates metrics and what other external providers are needed for the evaluation is not defined by the reference architecture, as the specific requirements are dependent on the concrete evaluation requirements at hand and *Evaluator* components can also forward the generation of measurements to *External Evaluators* outside of the scope of the proposed system. To provide a clear separation of responsibilities, an *Evaluator* is supposed to provide evaluation measurements for only one evaluation dimension. The entire process of measurement generation is exposed with the interface *Generate Measurements*.

DMP Harvester Service

This component unifies the access to data needed for the evaluation of maDMPs to provide a single endpoint to fetch the DMP itself including the associated ontologies and related contextual data, as well as to orchestrate the collection of this information from a variety of sources by accessing the interfaces provided by the *DMP Loader* and *Context*

Loader components. To that extent, it exposes the interface *Harvest Extended DMP* which provides access to all this information.

Figure 8 shows a detailed view of the subcomponents contained in the *DMP Harvester Service*. It is made up of the components *DMP Provider*, *Context Provider*, *Inference Engine* and *Data Provider*.

DMP Provider: The *DMP Provider* is responsible for loading normalised DMPs from relevant *DMP Loader* components. As actual retrieval of maDMPs from available sources and normalisation to a uniform format is the responsibility of the individual *DMP Loader*, the *DMP Provider* acts as a bridge, connecting and exposing different instances of *DMP Loader* components with other components of the framework by exposing the *Load DMP* endpoint.

Figure 8 - Building block of the DMP Harvester Service.

Context Provider: The *Context Provider* component facilitates the communication between different instances of *Context Loader* components, which in turn collect and transform information regarding a given DMP from various sources such as SKGs and repositories. As a result, the *Context Provider* provides unified access to available instances of *Context Loader* components via the provided *Get Context* interface.

Data Provider: The *Data Provider* collects information regarding DMPs from the *DMP Provider* and the corresponding contextual information from the *Context Provider*. It uses the interfaces of the *Inference Engine* component to expand the information that is implicitly available in the given DMP. Furthermore, the *Data Provider* component uses the *Data Store* component to store the DMP and the contextual information collected and provides the *Harvest Extended DMP* interface to export this information to other components of the framework.

DMP Indicator Service

This component coordinates the evaluation process for a DMP and exposes the interfaces *Evaluate DMP* for the process of the DMP evaluation and *Generate Evaluation Report* for the process of generating measurement reports in the form of aggregations and averages of measurements. The indicator service component retrieves the DMP, ontologies and additional context from the *DMP Harvester Service* and stores the evaluation result using the data store component. It coordinates the invocation of *Evaluator* components and provides them with the data they need for the generation of indicators. The indicators collected from the individual *Evaluator* components are collected and persisted at the end of the evaluation process.

Figure 9 shows the conceptual building blocks of the proposed *DMP Indicator service*. The service is composed of the subcomponents *Evaluation Manager*, *Evaluation Provider* and *Metric Aggregator*.

Figure 9 - Building blocks of the DMP Indicator service.

Evaluation Manager: The *Evaluation Manager* component is the central access point to request and retrieve quality indicators for a DMP by providing the interface *Evaluate DMP* to start a DMP evaluation process and *Generate Evaluation Report* to provide summaries of quality measurements. The component facilitates the generation of quality measurements by managing the collection of the necessary information through the interfaces of the *DMP Harvester Service* and gathers the generated measurements from the *Evaluation Provider* to which it passes the maDMP and other information.

Evaluation Provider: The *Evaluation Provider* is responsible for the integration of *Evaluator* components and provides a unified gateway for the *DMP Indicator Service* to access these components by providing the *Get Measurements* interface. It invokes *Evaluator* components, based on the evaluation requirements, and returns a collective result that contains the individual quality measurements of the respective *Evaluator* components. We recommend using the DMPQV data structure. This data structure is described in the section of data structure for the communication of quality indicators and measurements between the components involved.

Measurement Aggregator: The *Measurement Aggregator* exposes the interface *Aggregate Measurements* through which it retrieves quality indicators and processes them to provide a better view of the result of the evaluation of a DMP by aggregating the measurements and calculating averages as described in the proposed of the business architecture.

DATA STRUCTURE USED BETWEEN COMPONENTS

DMPQV: In this section we present the data structure that can describe the result of the evaluation of the DMP. The data structured modelled, shown in **Figure 10** that provides a standard for storage and sharing of the results of the evaluation of a DMP.

While designing this conceptual data structure, it was designed on building on existing standards. Therefore, the core of this model is based on the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) which is a W3C standard to describe data quality measurements. As such, it reuses definitions from other schemas such as Dublin Core (DC) and PROV Vocabulary (PROV). The data structure extended it with additional elements, to cover the specific requirements for representing DMP measurement results. Given that this data structure is an extension of DQV, we refer to the model as Data Management Plan Quality Vocabulary (DMPQV).

The core of the proposed data structure is a *Metric*, which provides information on what is being measured and how to categorise a measurement regarding its *Dimension* as well as *Category*. A *Metric* further provides information on the expected data type and value ranges. It could be that there exist metrics that, while measuring an aspect of the same dimension, form their own subgroup, which is why metrics can be assigned to a *MetricGroup*. Metrics specify a quality aspect of a DMP but can be a result of the application of individual tests, which are specified by a *MetricTestDefinitions*. A *Metric* is a template for a *QualityMeasurement*, which provides a value for the defined metric at a given *LifecycleStage* of a DMP and also provides a reference to individual *TestResult* instances. Quality Measurements point to the part of the maDMP which has been evaluated, which can be an entity or a specific value of an entity. Furthermore, Quality Measurements can refer to *Guidance* to provide suggestions for improvements, as well as to provenance information from the evaluation provided by *SoftwareAgent*.

Figure 10 - Data structure used to represent the result of the evaluation DMPQV.

Context Data Structure:

As DCS maDMPs contain references to external sources in the form of PIDs and other identifiers, the design recognised the need to resolve these references to provide an evaluation context for further evaluation of the maDMP, which has also been identified as a requirement. The design provides a standard representation of this context to complement DCS DMPs. To that extent, **Figure 11** shows the proposed data structure.

The main element of this conceptual component is *Context*. This conceptual element contains the data itself, which can be of arbitrary nature. To allow the interpretation by a consumer, a reference to the schema used is provided by the *Vocabulary* element. In addition, the context element also provides provenance information from which the

information is gathered by referencing a *Source* component. Finally, a context has to be anchored with some entity or property of a maDMP which is made possible by linking to a *DMPLocation* component that holds the necessary information to address a DCS DMP.

Figure 11 - Data structure used to specify context.

2.2 Content Standardisation (Service Input)

This category centers around the **development and standardisation of the criteria and frameworks** that the evaluation service uses. It involves creating the rubrics and templates that will guide the evaluation process.

Key tasks include:

- **Developing rubrics:** Creating detailed criteria for evaluating different aspects of DMPs, such as data sharing, metadata standards, and preservation. The goal is to make these rubrics more objective and quantifiable for automation.
- **Standardising DMP templates:** Developing standardized formats for DMPs that ensure they include all necessary components for automated evaluation, while also allowing flexibility for different research disciplines and funding bodies.
- **Creating policies:** Crafting the policies that ensure alignment with international standards like FAIR principles and Open Science policies, and that guide the future evolution of automated DMP evaluations.

- **Harmonising content:** Aligning rubrics, templates, and policies with emerging research data management practices and requirements from funding agencies, ensuring they stay relevant and adaptable.

2.2.1 Rubrics

Rubrics are tools that provide detailed criteria for evaluating DMPs. They offer clear definitions of what constitutes a good DMP, outlining specific requirements for sections such as data sharing, metadata, data preservation, and ethical considerations. While rubrics such as those from Science Europe and the RDA have been developed, they are primarily qualitative and difficult to automate. Current rubrics often require human evaluators to assess whether a DMP meets the specified criteria, which can introduce variability in evaluations. Some rubrics are based on domain-specific requirements, while others focus on more general aspects of research data management. The challenge with these rubrics is that they often rely on subjective judgment, which makes it hard to automate the evaluation process. Additionally, rubrics need to be updated regularly to keep up with emerging standards in data management and evolving research practices [4]. Consequently, there is a need to develop more objective, quantifiable rubrics that can be integrated into automated systems for evaluating maDMPs effectively.

In summary, the maDMP Evaluation Framework aims to ensure that machine-actionable DMPs meet the highest standards of data management. By refining policies, standardising templates, and enhancing rubrics, the framework will support more consistent, efficient, and automated evaluations, ultimately improving the quality of research data management practices.

2.2.2 Templates

Templates are an integral part of the maDMP evaluation framework. They provide standardised formats that researchers can follow when creating their DMPs, ensuring that all necessary components are included. However, these templates vary across funding bodies, regions, and research disciplines. The challenge lies in harmonising these templates to create a more universally accepted framework that can be integrated into automated systems. Furthermore, templates must be flexible enough to accommodate various disciplines, allowing for customisation based on specific research needs while maintaining alignment with broader DMP standards [5]. The use of machine-actionable templates, which can be processed and evaluated automatically, is gaining traction, but there is still progress to be made in standardising these templates across multiple platforms and communities.

2.2.3 Policies

Policies surrounding maDMP evaluation focus on ensuring that the evaluation framework aligns with international standards and principles such as the FAIR data principles and Open Science policies. At a policy level, there is a push for standardised approaches to

DMP evaluation across disciplines and institutions, ensuring consistency and transparency. Many national and international funding agencies, including those in the European Union, have established guidelines for DMPs, but these policies often lack a unified approach to the automated evaluation of DMPs. Policies must therefore evolve to support the automation of DMP evaluations, promoting consistency in reporting and ensuring that research data is managed in a manner that supports reproducibility and long-term access.

3 Identified Gaps and Opportunities

Our analysis of DMP templates, evaluation rubrics, and guidance documents that are currently used by the pilots provided valuable input for improving the DMP evaluation framework in our next iteration. It should be noted that our data collection represents a combination of European, national, and international bodies, as well as research support initiatives that cater to specific academic and research needs. ([See Annex for the full list and comparisons](#))

Below, we summarise our findings per type of material:

Table 2 - Observations on Templates.

TEMPLATES ARE FORMS CREATED BY FUNDING ORGANISATIONS. THEY CONTAIN QUESTIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH PROJECTS THAT RESEARCHERS NEED TO ANSWER, ALONG WITH THE NECESSARY GUIDANCE/INSTRUCTIONS TO SUPPORT THEM RESPOND APPROPRIATELY.	
General observations	Specific Examples
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural Differences: Templates vary in length and structure—some include both categorisation and numbering of questions, while others feature only one or neither. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common Questions: Most templates share questions related to data backup, data availability licensing, and interoperability standards.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Content: All templates emphasise metadata, documentation, and quality control. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unique Features: Some templates, like DART and NSF, specify which directorates can use each question, and DART introduces sections like "Additional Questions of Interest".
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Question Variability: Many questions are common across templates, though wording may differ slightly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Template Variations: BELSPO adds a question on data availability licensing, while ERC introduces unique interoperability questions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detail and Guidance: The level of detail varies—some templates use broad, summary-style questions, while others require specialised and technical responses. Certain templates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Administrative Focus: Templates like NCN and UGentGeneric place a stronger emphasis on administrative procedures or response formats.

include supplementary questions, guidance on what to consider, or references to relevant questions.	
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Table 3 - Observations on Guidance

GUIDANCE REFERS TO THE NARRATIVES THAT HELP RESEARCHERS UNDERSTAND HOW TO RESPOND TO DMP QUESTIONS. THEY MAY BE FOUND AS SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL, AS INSTRUCTIONS NEXT TO THE QUESTIONS OR EVEN BE DIRECTLY CONNECTED TO THE QUESTIONS AS EXAMPLES.	
General observations	Specific Examples
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed vs. General Guidance: Some templates focus on detailed instructions for completing the DMP, while others offer general guidance with less specific direction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed Instructions: SE, DART, and SND provide more step-by-step guidance, with SND also emphasizing administrative details.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embedded vs. External Guidance: Some templates embed guidance directly in the template, whereas others rely on external guidance sheets or rubrics for additional support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embedded vs. External Guidance: DART and SND embed instructions directly in the template, whereas FWF and General Finnish rely on external documents for more detailed guidance.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on Specific Sections: Some templates provide more detailed guidance for specific sections like administrative information, while others offer general best practices for the entire DMP process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on Administrative Information: SND provides extra details on administrative sections that are more extensive than in other templates.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples and Best Practices: Some templates include examples and possible answers to clarify the template's sections, while others focus on providing best practices and advice on what to avoid when filling out the DMP. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best Practices and Avoidance Tips: Finnish and FWF offer best practices and cautionary advice to guide researchers in the right direction.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples and Answers: DART is particularly helpful with its inclusion of examples and possible answers, while others focus more on general guidance.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term storage and transparency: NWO enforces the

	need for long-term data storage (at least 10 years) and the provision of persistent identifiers to monitor the citation and reuse of the data.
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Table 4 - Observations on Rubrics

RUBRICS ARE SETS OF CRITERIA/GUIDES USED TO EVALUATE THE QUALITY OF DMPs AND THEY ARE LINKED WITH PERFORMANCE LEVELS.	
General observations	Specific Examples
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rubric Basis and Inspiration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Many rubrics are inspired by or based on SE and European Commission guidelines, ensuring alignment with well-established frameworks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative Details: Rubrics like FWF and SE provide more specific administrative details, such as version control and required data management elements.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance Levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Terminology for performance levels varies across rubrics, often addressing completeness of information. ○ Some rubrics differentiate performance levels into terms such as “Excellent,” “Satisfactory,” and “Poor,” while others use broader classifications. ○ Wording differences exist across rubrics, particularly when addressing administrative details or specific requirements. ○ Some rubrics align in performance levels for certain questions, but their descriptions may vary slightly, reflecting different interpretation or priorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples and Guidance: DART and PHAIDRA differ from traditional rubrics by providing examples and a scoring system rather than detailed rubric performance levels.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity and Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Concrete examples are often lacking, especially for the “Insufficiently 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with European Standards: Rubrics like H2020, HEU, and ERC closely follow European Commission guidelines,

<p>Addressed” leading to ambiguity in interpretation of performance levels.</p>	<p>category, potential in of</p> <p>ensuring alignment with Open Science policies and data management standards.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified Evaluations: SND opts for a checklist approach, while NCN does not include detailed performance levels, offering a simpler evaluation format.

3.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings from our analysis, we present a first set of recommendations for improving the DMP evaluation framework, with the ultimate goal of enhancing efficiency, consistency, and interoperability in research data management.

- **Standardise Terminology and Performance Levels in Rubrics:**

To reduce ambiguity and ensure consistency across evaluations, it’s crucial to standardize terminology and performance levels in rubrics. This includes clarifying terms like “Excellent,” “Satisfactory,” and “Poor” and providing clear, actionable examples for each level of performance, especially for "Insufficiently Addressed" categories.

- **Embed Detailed Guidance Within Templates:**

Providing more detailed, step-by-step guidance within DMP templates, rather than relying on external documents, will help researchers more easily navigate complex sections. This could include specific instructions for data licensing, long-term storage, and compliance with funder requirements.

- **Provide Concrete Examples and Best Practices:**

Incorporating examples and best practices directly into templates, similar to DART’s approach, will help clarify expectations for researchers, especially for more technical or complex sections. Examples of well-answered questions can guide researchers and improve the overall quality of DMP submissions.

- **Ensure Compatibility with Machine-Actionable DMPs (maDMPs):**

Rubrics, templates, and guidance should be aligned with machine-actionable DMP frameworks to facilitate automated evaluations. This would reduce the manual effort

involved in DMP creation and evaluation, allowing for more efficient and scalable processes.

- **Focus on Long-term Data Management and Transparency:**

Templates and rubrics should place more emphasis on long-term data storage, transparency, and the use of persistent identifiers to track data reuse and citations, as seen in the NWO template. This will align with Open Science and FAIR principles, supporting data longevity and accountability.

- **Simplify Administrative Sections Without Losing Detail:**

While some templates focus heavily on administrative details, there is an opportunity to simplify these sections without losing critical information. Clearer formatting and more intuitive question structures can make administrative requirements more accessible to researchers without sacrificing compliance.

4 Upcoming Activities

This activity has expanded beyond the original scope outlined in the proposal, driven by the need to develop new materials and address gaps in the current landscape. As a result, the project will continue to evolve with additional activities that will inform future versions of the DMP evaluation service and its subsequent iterations.

The next phase will focus on gathering more specific, targeted insights from funders. It has become clear that one-on-one interviews with funders, rather than broad surveys, will be a more effective approach to understanding their unique needs and requirements. This method will provide valuable, nuanced insights that existing DMP evaluation rubrics do not fully capture, ultimately leading to the creation of more adaptable templates and guidelines that better align with funders' and research organizations' expectations.

Following this, interviews with data stewards and research support staff will be conducted to fine-tune the survey questions. This engagement will ensure that the survey remains focused and relevant, addressing key concerns from the research support community. These insights, alongside the ongoing dissemination of templates and rubrics, will further guide the evolution of the DMP evaluation framework.

The end result of this process will be the development of flexible, adaptive DMP evaluation templates and guidelines. These tools will help standardize and enhance the assessment of DMPs across the research community, contributing to the overall improvement of the DMP evaluation service.

5 Conclusion and Next steps

To support the development of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs), we have provided clear specifications for the service, focusing on completeness, quality, validation, and alignment with the OSTrails Architecture and Interoperability Frameworks. This work is split into two complementary actions: **Technical Specifications (Service Development)** and **Content Standardisation (Service Input)**. These actions are essential for ensuring the service meets the needs of the research community and drives improvements in research data management.

The transition to maDMPs is a critical step in improving efficiency and automation in research data management. As research data becomes more complex, systems that streamline DMP creation and evaluation are increasingly necessary, ensuring compliance with funder requirements and the FAIR principles. While existing DMP rubrics are valuable, they are not designed for large-scale automation. By adopting machine-readable formats, maDMPs facilitate automatic validation and updates, reducing manual effort and enhancing consistency in evaluations.

However, challenges remain in integrating maDMPs with existing frameworks. Issues such as the lack of standardization, subjective evaluation methods, and funder-specific requirements must be addressed to enable seamless adoption. These challenges can be overcome through the continued development of flexible, interoperable rubrics that balance quantitative and qualitative criteria, paving the way for a standardized, automated DMP ecosystem.

The **maDMP Evaluation Framework** plays a crucial role in advancing DMP standards. Although automated evaluations are not yet widespread, the framework will contribute to the enhancement of the **DMP Common Standard**, supporting automated assessments. By offering clear, actionable criteria, it will help ensure that evaluations are more efficient, consistent, and scalable in the future.

To further refine DMP practices, we will conduct a survey with researchers, data stewards, funders, and research support staff, including librarians. This survey, alongside one-on-one interviews mobilises key pilot stakeholders to gather feedback to inform on the one hand the improvements needed in existing DMP evaluation frameworks and on the other support the ongoing development and implementation of maDMP solutions. Based on this feedback, we will share recommendations to improve the materials and support the pilots.

6 Annex: Sources of Templates, Guidance, and Rubrics

A complete mapping of the material can be found as supplementary data in our [Zenodo community](#). Below, the list of organisations represented in our analysis.

Table 55 - Reference Table: Templates, Guidance, and Rubrics

NAME OF TEMPLATES, GUIDANCE, AND RUBRICS	LINK
Guidance on the Evaluation of Data Management Plans (Science Europe)	https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/research-data-management/
FWF Data Management Plan (DMP) Evaluation Rubric	https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science/research-data-management
FWF Data Management Plan (DMP) Guidelines and Template	https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science/research-data-management
Rubric for assessment of NSF data management plans	https://osf.io/eurd9
Generic DMP Evaluation Rubric (Ghent University)	https://osf.io/2z5g3
Horizon Europe DMP Evaluation Rubric	https://osf.io/fza4t
Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP Evaluation Rubric	https://osf.io/fc8q5
FWO DMP Evaluation Rubric	https://osf.io/dhpr3
ERC DMP Evaluation Rubric	https://osf.io/racgq
BELSPO DMP Evaluation Rubric	https://osf.io/cjazy
Guidance for using the DART Rubric to assess NSF data management plans	https://osf.io/y9gze
General Finnish DMP guidance 2021	https://zenodo.org/records/5242629
Finnish DMP evaluation guidance	https://zenodo.org/records/4762326

Evaluation rubric for DMP analysis (PHAIDRA)	https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail/o:1165631
Checklist for Data Management Plan (SND)	https://zenodo.org/records/6424769
NWO Data Management Plan Assessment Rubric	https://zenodo.org/records/10143397
Guidelines for applicants to complete the Data Management Plan form in the proposal (NCN)	https://ncn.gov.pl/sites/default/files/pliki/regulamin/wytyczne_zarzadzanie_danymi_06_2020_ang.pdf

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